

Announcement

When the first edition of *Standard Evaluation System for Rice* was printed in 1975, it was agreed that the system would be updated after several years of use. The world's rice scientists rapidly and widely adopted the standard scoring system and are now making recommendations to the International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) for its improvement.

The IRTP plans to print the second edition of the *Standard Evaluation System for Rice* during 1978. Each scientist who has used the system is encouraged to make recommendations for improving the scales of particular traits. Suggestions received by April 15, 1978 will be discussed by participants at the International Rice Research Conference in April 1978; the revised publication will be printed about June 1978.

Submit recommendations to: International Rice Testing Program, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

before the cold nights begin, but they yield lower because their vegetative phase is shorter. The local aus varieties are better adapted to direct seeding; farmers plant them early to extend the growing season.

Farmers generally gave higher levels of productivity in 1975 was about 15% management to the HYV than to the local higher than in 1976. The rainfall pattern rices. More farmers applied higher rates of during grain filling probably explains the fertilizers at more balanced doses to the difference. ~~W~~ HYV and weeded them more often than they did the local rices. The average

IR26 does well as gogorancah crop in Indonesia

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Gogorancah is the direct seeding of rice on moist aerobic soil. From 30 to 40 days after seeding, the fields are banded and allowed to flood. Farmers along the north coastal plain of Java have extensively followed this culture for years.

Seven lowland rice varieties were tested on farmers' fields near Indramayu, West Java, to determine their yield potential when grown under gogorancah culture at the beginning of the wet

Varietal testing for gogorancah rice culture. Cropping systems research, Indramayu, Indonesia, 1975-76.

Variety	Maturity (DS) ^a	Plant height (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Daily production (kg/ha)
IR28	105	95	4.4	42.4
B-9C	110	96	3.6	32.1
IR30	110	95	3.8	34.2
C4-63G	125	115	5.6	44.6
IR26	125	101	5.9	47.0
IR34	135	137	3.1	23.2
Pelita I/1	140	141	5.2	37.2

^aDays after sowing in seedbed or direct seeding in field.

season. Pelita I/1 was used as a check.

IR26 yielded the highest (5.9 t/ha), closely followed by C4-63G (5.6 t/ha) and Pelita I/1 (5.2 t/ha) (see table). IR28 harvest 15 days earlier and produce and other less known varieties yielded higher yields than those who grow considerably less. In terms of production per day IR26 was first (47.0 kg/day) followed by C4-63G (44.6 kg/day) and IR28 (42.4 kg/day).

Pelita I/1 produced only 37.2 kg/day.

IR26 appears to be very suitable for gogorancah. Farmers who use IR26 can and Pelita I/1 (5.2 t/ha) (see table). IR28 harvest 15 days earlier and produce and other less known varieties yielded higher yields than those who grow considerably less. In terms of production per day IR26 was first (47.0 kg/day) followed by C4-63G (44.6 kg/day) and IR28 (42.4 kg/day). Furthermore, IR26 is tolerant of Pelita I/1. Furthermore, IR26 is tolerant of the brown planthopper, a serious pest of the Indramayu area. ~~W~~

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